

SIMULATION OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF A THREE DIMENSIONAL COMPOSITE

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Abstract — We propose an approach to characterize the mechanical properties of interlock woven composite structures and particularly to solve the problems associated with the creation of these complex geometries and their discretization into a conform mesh. Once the model is meshed and the symmetry conditions are defined, the properties are obtained by homogenization. Complex weaves can be automatically processed with this technique.

1. Introduction

The work proposed here is devoted to the prediction and the characterization of the mechanical behavior of interlock woven composite structures [1] [2]. One of the difficulties of this meso-macro approach is to reproduce faithfully the geometry of these architectures with complex shapes and to obtain a Representative Volume Element (RVE). Once this complex step is achieved, the mechanical properties of the composite can be thereafter obtained by homogenization from a finite element analysis. Our aim is to develop a robust methodology to predict and to optimize the mechanical properties of a wide range of weaves embedded in resin. Woven composites studied are 2.5D interlock composite. The crossing weft yarns and warp yarns in three directions authorizes an important number of architectures and can provide to the resulting composite a high structural potential.

The difficulties to generate a RVE of such structures are well known: interpenetration and contacts between yarns, meshing of thin resin layers at interfaces, determination of the orientation of the fibers at all points of the structure. To address these problems with a finite element analysis, a discretization by voxels [3] [4] may provide a flexible solution but only offers a rough approximation of geometry. Other approaches have been proposed [5] based on the management of contact by specific models such as Multifill [6] or on the use of geometric models which reduce the number of intersections [7] or even correct the interpenetrations [8].

We propose an approach which consists of creating a geometric model of the yarns limiting or controlling the intersections and the contacts, defining RVE periodic, meshing this RVE by tetrahedral with compatible meshes at the interfaces, then using periodic homogenization techniques on the RVE to obtain the mechanical properties. The results are compared to other modeling from the literature [9].

2. Mesh a RVE

Our research focuses on obtaining a computational model of 2.5D interlock woven composite materials [1-12]. One of the scientific challenges is to optimize these architectures and in particular, the interlacing between weft and warp yarns in order to give to the structure a greater resistance in three directions. As we plan to optimize the weaving of these structures, it is essential to develop a robust methodology to obtain finite element models for various geometric parameters of weaving.

Create or retrieve geometry is the first step towards solving the problem. Then the model has to be meshed and this blocking point is the main goal of this work. The yarns are in contact. We chose to solve the problem by producing a consistent mesh at the interfaces between surfaces. Therefore, contacts or intersections must be detected with accuracy and robustness. The main difficulties that are often highlighted and which must be properly addressed are:

- ❖ Create a consistent mesh at the interfaces between surfaces;
- ❖ Mesh the resin and therefore avoid creating too close surface elements. Indeed, at contact areas, the surfaces are tangent and "crushed." Even if we perform a conformable mesh at the interfaces, the risk is to get, in the best case, very flat elements at adjacent area of the contact area what may impede the convergence of the mesh generator .

Our developed approach is automatic; meshes are necessarily made of tetrahedra [13]. A less realistic issue could be to move away the contact's surfaces to "pass" the resin. In order to realize a mesh, a space must be left around the common contour of two surfaces facing each other. In addition, the local mesh size must be of the order of magnitude of the spacing between the surfaces in order to fill this space with well shaped. In other words, one must realize an adaptive mesh at vicinity of contact zone and the mesh size around the contour of intersection must be a user parameter. It corresponds to the maximum volume of resin that we want to put in this area. A brief summary of the different stages of the construction of the mesh is proposed.

2.1 Creation of the geometry

A "realistic" geometry that minimizes intersections between yarns is created: the material consists of layers based on tissue. To clarify the speech, we assume that the fabrics are made of unidirectional fibers crossed 90°. We can thus define an array of wefts yarns along which the warp yarns are undulating.

We have created an analytical model defining paths of yarns along the wefts yarns. Normal cross sections to the curve are assumed to be elliptical. The path of warp yarns is defined by the position above or below sections [7-12]. The proposed geometric model limits the number of intersections between yarns, allows contacts and enables an

accurate control of inter-yarns space for the resin (Fig. 2.) Contact areas can be identified analytically.

2.2. Adapted mesh

A mesh is performed in the parameter space of the surface of the yarns. In this space, the initial mesh of each yarn is a $L^e \times L^f$ grid dimension where L^e is perimeter of the ellipse and L^f is the estimated length of the neutral fiber. The mesh is thus performed in space $[0, L^f] \times [0, L^e]$. The idea is to cut recursively the initial regular mesh by dividing the cells containing points into contact, close to other yarns or faces of the RVE. The idea is to get an adapted mesh and avoid the generation of flat elements. Each element of the initial grid constitutes a quadtree. This technique can be seen as a multi-quadtree method. Depending on the status of the points with respect to the cell (contact, interpenetration, outside), we can define the position of the interface contour on the adapted grid as the marching cubes method [14]. Cutting rules are defined. The ultimate level of mesh refinement is given a priori. Figure 3 shows the adaptation of the grid of a yarn in 3D space. Refined areas correspond to contacts between yarns or at the proximity of one face of the RVE.

To obtain a conform mesh at interfaces, we chose that the warp yarns inherit (by projection) the intersections created on the wefts yarns. The final mesh of surfaces is obtained by re-meshing the points generated by the adaptive grid.

Fig. 1. Network of weft yarns and the path of the warps yarns

Fig. 2. Space management of the inter-yarns at a contact area

2.3. Creating the box RVE

The meshing of all yarns and all the contact areas has been made. The yarns are trimmed to ensure the conditions of symmetry and periodicity of the RVE. The last step before the three-dimensional meshing is to create the faces of the RVE (Fig. 4).

2.4. Volume mesh

The mesh is made of 4 nodes or 10 nodes tetrahedral [13]. The fibers of yarns of weaves studied have an orthotropic behavior. Therefore, it is essential to determine the orientation of the fiber everywhere in the structure. The orientation is determined at the center of gravity of each element. Given a point in a yarn, we determine by minimization the normal projection of the point on the neutral axis. We can remark that the same test is performed many times during the process of detection of the intersections.

In practice an angular amplitude corresponding to the minimum and maximum angle, we define a material for a range of orientations. In other words, the number of materials is limited; we can define a priori a number of materials and create a material for every 1°, for example. Figures 5 illustrate this determination for a complex RVE. All the materials are shown in the left. The right one shows the materials whose orientation is close to 0°.

Fig. 3. 3D tree grid quaternary. Preparation for mesh a yarn

Fig. 4. Relimitation yarns and construction of the "box" of RVE

Fig. 5. Determination of orthotropic directions

3. Determination of the homogenized mechanical properties

To validate the methodology of construction and mesh of the RVE presented above (see section 2), two composite interlocks studied by Hallal *et al.* [9] are considered: an Interlock type 1 denoted as H2 and an interlock type 4 denoted as 69). We thus have for these two composites modeling results in the elastic regime (see Table 3). In the case of the interlock H2, it is a model of about 300000 elements, 33000 nodes and 99000 therefore degrees of freedom (dof). For Interlock 69, model is made of about 70,000 elements, 70,000 nodes, therefore 210,000 dof.

By applying our meshing methodology, we obtain for each of the materials considered (Interlock H2 and Interlock 69) two RVE, the first consists of T4 elements and the second of T10 elements. Thus, for each case, the influence of degree of the shape function considered (linear or quadratic) can be estimated. For Interlock H2, the RVE is made of 140,000 elements (77,000 dof by considering T4 elements T4 and 580,000 dof with T10 elements). In the case of the interlock 69, the RVE is made of 93,000 elements (51,000 dof by considering T4 elements and 380,000 dof with T10 elements). Figures 6 and Figure 7 illustrate the RVE mesh of the Interlock H2 and of the interlock 69, respectively.

Given the periodicity of the considered composites, the determination of homogenized properties of the RVE requires the consideration of periodic conditions before the simulation of different loading cases.

3.1. Periodicity of the RVE and determination of homogenized mechanical properties

The geometry of the studied materials imposes the definition of periodic boundaries conditions on the RVE [15-17]. These are applied by ABAQUS via the function *equation. As already described in a previous study by Halal *et al.* [9], nine constraint equations must be imposed between all pairs of periodic nodes of the different faces of the RVE (except on the edges).

In both considered cases here (Interlock H2 and 69), the composite is assumed orthotropic. Its compliance tensor S is written from E_i , ν_{ij} and G_{ij} (i and j from 1 to 3) which are the elastic constants of the orthotropic material: the Young's modulus, the Poisson's ratios and shear modules in the considered directions i and j.

These elastic constants are determined by 6 different load case simulations on the RVE: 3 tensile tests (along x, y and z) and 3 shear tests (according to the xy, xz and yz planes).

Assuming that the 6 faces of the RVE are respectively positioned in the global reference in ABAQUS x_{\min} , x_{\max} , y_{\min} , y_{\max} , z_{\min} et z_{\max} , in the case of a tensile test along the x direction or a shear test in the xy plane; we can write, as a function of an arbitrarily chosen displacement U , the nine constraint equations governing the movement (u_1 , u_2 et u_3 according to x, y and z respectively) of each node of each face of RVE (see [9]):

Fig. 6. Mesh of Interlock H2: Mesh of RVE (a), Resin (b), Warps and wefts yarns (c)

Fig. 7. Mesh of Interlock H2: Mesh of RVE (a), Resin (b), Warps and wefts yarns (c)

• **Tensile test along to x.**

➤ On the faces $x = x_{\min}$ et $x = x_{\max}$ as follows:

$$u_1(x_{\min}, y, z) = 0 ; u_1(x_{\max}, y, z) = U ; \quad (1)$$

$$u_2(x_{\max}, y, z) - u_2(x_{\min}, y, z) = 0 ; \quad (2)$$

$$u_3(x_{\max}, y, z) - u_3(x_{\min}, y, z) = 0. \quad (3)$$

➤ On the faces $y = y_{\min}$ et $y = y_{\max}$ as follows:

$$u_1(x, y_{\max}, z) - u_1(x, y_{\min}, z) = 0 ; \quad (4)$$

$$u_2(x, y_{\max}, z) - u_2(x, y_{\min}, z) = 0 ; \quad (5)$$

$$u_3(x, y_{\max}, z) - u_3(x, y_{\min}, z) = 0. \quad (6)$$

➤ On the faces $z = z_{\min}$ et $z = z_{\max}$ as follows:

$$u_1(x, y, z_{\max}) - u_1(x, y, z_{\min}) = 0 ; \quad (7)$$

$$u_2(x, y, z_{\max}) - u_2(x, y, z_{\min}) = 0 ; \quad (8)$$

$$u_3(x, y, z_{\max}) - u_3(x, y, z_{\min}) = 0. \quad (9)$$

The Young's modulus E_x is then calculated from the equation:

$$E_x = \frac{F_x \cdot (x_{\max} - x_{\min})}{(y_{\max} - y_{\min}) \cdot (z_{\max} - z_{\min}) \cdot U} \quad (10)$$

Where F_x is the force applied during the tensile test on the face $x = x_{\max}$.

Similarly, with tensile tests along the y and z directions respectively, the Young's modulus E_y and E_z can be calculated. The 3 Young's modulus of orthotropic composite known, we determine the 3 Poisson's ratios such as the relationship $\underline{\varepsilon} = \underline{S} : \underline{\sigma}$ is verified.

• **Shear test in the xy plane.**

➤ On the faces $x = x_{\min}$ et $x = x_{\max}$ as follows:

$$u_1(x_{\max}, y, z) - u_1(x_{\min}, y, z) = 0 ; \quad (11)$$

$$u_2(x_{\max}, y, z) - u_2(x_{\min}, y, z) = 0 ; \quad (12)$$

$$u_3(x_{\max}, y, z) - u_3(x_{\min}, y, z) = 0. \quad (13)$$

➤ On the faces $y = y_{\min}$ et $y = y_{\max}$ as follows:

$$u_1(x, y_{\min}, z) = 0 ; u_1(x, y_{\max}, z) = U ; \quad (14)$$

$$u_2(x, y_{\max}, z) - u_2(x, y_{\min}, z) = 0 ; \quad (15)$$

$$u_3(x, y_{\max}, z) - u_3(x, y_{\min}, z) = 0. \quad (16)$$

➤ On the faces $z = z_{\min}$ et $z = z_{\max}$ as follows:

$$u_1(x, y, z_{\max}) - u_1(x, y, z_{\min}) = 0 ; \quad (17)$$

$$u_2(x, y, z_{\max}) - u_2(x, y, z_{\min}) = 0 ; \quad (18)$$

$$u_3(x, y, z_{\max}) - u_3(x, y, z_{\min}) = 0. \quad (19)$$

The shear modulus G_{xy} is then calculated from the equation:

$$G_{xy} = \frac{F_x \cdot (y_{\max} - y_{\min})}{(y_{\max} - y_{\min}) \cdot (y_{\max} - y_{\min}) \cdot U} \quad (20)$$

Where F_x is the force applied during the test on the $y = y_{\max}$ face.

By 2 other shear tests in the yz and xz planes, the shear modulus G_{yz} and G_{zx} can be calculated.

3.2. Results of numerical simulations.

In Interlock composite, the matrix (also called resin) which is linking all the yarns. In the studied materials (Interlock H2 and 69), the matrix is epoxy. It will be assumed isotropic; the elastic properties are shown in Table 1 (see [1]).

Young's modulus E^m (Mpa)	Poisson's ratios ν^m	Shear modulus G^m (Mpa)
2890	0.35	1070

Table 1: Mechanical properties of epoxy

The designation of the used yarns (fibers in resin) is 'T300J' (provided by SNECMA, cf. [1]). The fibers of these yarns are made of carbon and epoxy (same epoxy in the matrix). The mechanical behavior of the carbon fibers is assumed orthotropic with 9 elastic constants defined in Table 2a (see [1]). In order to compare the results of our predictions with those obtained by Hallal *et al.*[9], the mechanical behavior of weft and warp yarns is determined from the Chamis model [17]:

E_{11} (Mpa)	E_{22} (Mpa)	E_{33} (Mpa)	G_{12} (Mpa)	G_{13} (Mpa)	G_{23} (Mpa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
230000	15000	15000	50000	50000	5769	0.278	0.278	0.3

Table 2a: Mechanical properties of carbon fibers

Composite	Warp yarns		Weft yarns		Distance between yarns	
	Width	Thickness	Width	Thickness	Weft yarns	Warp yarns
	a_w (mm)	h_w (mm)	a_f (mm)	h_f (mm)	C_L (mm)	C_T (mm)
H2	1.9 ± 0.11	0.18 ± 0.03	1.7 ± 0.06	0.28 ± 0.03	0.4 ± 0.12	0.2 ± 0.08
69	4.4706 ± 0.3533	0.6471 ± 0.0133	3.163 ± 0.427	0.5882 ± 0.1084	2.8235 ± 0.5087	0.00 ± 0.06

Table 2b: Geometric properties of the composites H2 and 69

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= V^f E_{11}^f + V^m E^m \\ E_{22} &= \frac{E^m}{1 - \sqrt{V^f} (1 - E^m / E_{22}^f)} \\ \nu_{12} &= V^f \nu_{12}^f + V^m \nu^m \\ G_{12} &= \frac{G^m}{1 - \sqrt{V^f} (1 - G^m / G_{12}^f)} \\ G_{23} &= \frac{G^m}{1 - \sqrt{V^f} (1 - G^m / G_{23}^f)} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

V^f : volume fraction of carbon fibers in the yarns.
 V^m : volume fraction of the epoxy resin in the yarns.
 As shown in Hallal *et al.*, the volume fractions of fibers in the weft yarns and in the warp yarns are taken equal to 0.6 for the 2 interlock composites considered.

The composite are taken from the geometrical parameters previously described in the materials section (Table 2b). The geometric parameters needed in the geometrical modeling of the numerical and analytical models are defined as follow:

- L_x , L_y and L_z : the length, width and thickness of the RVE.
- a_w and a_f : are the widths of the warp and weft yarns.
- h_w and h_f : the thickness of the warp and weft yarns.
- C_L : distance between two adjacent weft yarns
- C_T : distance between two adjacent warp yarns.

The mechanical properties of yarns and resin constituting the two studied composites interlocks known, by the simulation of the 6 load case already described, we determine the homogenized mechanical properties of the two composites. The confrontations between our predictions and those obtained by Hallal *et al.* are summarized in Tables 3 and 4.

By considering a quadratic or a linear interpolation function, the simulations conducted on our RVE provide equivalent results; the maximum relative deviation is 7% on the calculation of G_{xy} in case of interlock 69. The number of DOF with T10 elements T10 is significantly higher than that obtained with T4 elements, the accuracy/time of the calculations seems to be good enough with T4 elements.

Compared to results obtained by Hallal *et al.*, there is however a relative difference of about 30% in the case of the interlock 69 (maximum on G_{yz} : 28.7%) and a relative difference of about 10% in the case of the H2 Interlock (maximum on G_{xy}).

4. Conclusion:

An innovative approach of RVE mesh of composite Interlock has been developed. This allows limiting the number of degrees of freedom of RVE by using an adaptive mesh only refined near the contacts between yarns. The implementation of this methodology for two interlock composites, found in the literature, allows the comparison of our results to those obtained with a large number of dof. It appears that the compromise obtained on accuracy compared to the time calculation gain must still be approved by a confrontation with experimental data.

Interlock H2	Type of elements	Ex (MPa)	Ey (MPa)	Ez (MPa)	Gxy (MPa)	Gxz (MPa)	Gyz (MPa)
Ali Hallal and al. [9]	T4+H8	54.82	25.93	7.87	3.22	2.24	2.94
Numerical simulation on the RVE	T4	57.10	26.40	7.20	2.90	2.30	2.70
	T10	57.01	24.60	7.10	2.81	2.27	2.60

Table 3: Comparison of predictions with those obtained by Hallal *et al.* for Interlock H2

Interlock 69	Type of elements	Ex (MPa)	Ey (MPa)	Ez (MPa)	Gxy (MPa)	Gxz (MPa)	Gyz (MPa)
Ali Hallal and al [9]	T4+H8	37.23	28.98	8.99	3.41	2.16	4.81
Numerical simulation on the RVE	T4	32.45	21.40	8.44	2.61	2.15	3.43
	T10	32.80	20.80	8.09	2.80	2.30	3.60

Table 4: Comparison of predictions with those obtained by Hallal *et al.* for Interlock 69

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